

usc school of music
presents

CARNIVAL
NIGHT

with

Jean Barr &
Armen Guzelimian
and friends

Friday, October 28, 1983
8:00 pm
Hancock Auditorium

Program

Andante and Variations, Op. 46 (Original Version) **Robert Schumann**

Jean Barr, piano
Armen Guzelimian, piano
Gabor Rejto, cello
Peter Rejto, cello
Richard Todd, French horn

Suite No. 2, Op. 17 **Sergei Rachmaninoff**

Introduction
Waltz
Romance
Tartantella

Armen Guzelimian, piano
Jean Barr, piano

INTERMISSION

Carnival of the Animals (Grand Zoological Fantasy) . . . **Camille Saint-Saëns**
with verses by Ogden Nash

Introduction
Royal March of the Lions
Cocks and Hens
Wild Jackass
Turtles
Elephants
Kangaroos
The Aquarium
The Mules
The Cuckoo in the Woods
The Birds
The Pianists
The Fossils
The Swan
Grand Finale

Charles Roe, Narrator
Jean Barr, piano
Armen Guzelimian, piano
Terry Stuhl, flute/piccolo
Mitchell Lurie, clarinet
Cynthia Stutt, violin
Susan Stone, violin
Milton Thomas, viola
Gabor Rejto, cello
David Young, double bass
Kenneth Watson, xylophone
Robert Fernandez, glockenspiel

Program Notes

Robert Schumann completed his *Andante con variazioni* for two pianofortes, two cellos and horn in late January, 1843, at the end of a year of extensive preoccupation with chamber music. He apparently was not entirely happy with what he had written – “I have only heard the Variations once,” he wrote several months later, “but they did not go particularly well. That sort of thing needs to be studied. It has something of the spirit of an elegy; I think I was rather melancholy when I composed it” – and in August he rescored the work for two pianos alone. The revision eliminated the introduction and an extensive series of variations near the end, which feature the cellos and horn rather prominently. Published in 1844 as his Op. 46, the revised version was premiered by Clara Schumann and Felix Mendelssohn.

Camille Saint-Saëns originally composed his *Carnival of the Animals* in the form of a suite for two pianos. It was written in 1886 for a private family gathering, and although it was later orchestrated, Saint-Saëns refused to publish it or have it publicly performed as long as he lived. Shortly before his death, Liszt expressed a wish to hear it, and Saint-Saëns organized a private performance for the composer. Liszt was said to have been enchanted with the quality of the orchestration and with the humor of the musical effects. Of particular amusement are the turtle-like parody of the famous can-can tune from Offenbach's *Orpheus in the Underworld*; the elephantine clumsiness of the *Waltz of the Sylphs* from Berlioz's *Damnation of Faust*; and the musical quote from the composer's own *Danse Macabre* in *The Fossils* – which also contains fragments of two famous French folk tunes and a snatch from *The Barber of Seville*. When Columbia Records decided to record the piece, Goddard Lieberson (the Executive Vice-President) conceived the idea of asking Ogden Nash to write epigrams to enhance the musical humor of the work. You will hear the marvelously hilarious results tonight.

Jean Barr